

Toxic metabolites produced in the blood in asthma.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

East Islip, NY USA 11730

This study describes for the first time toxic metabolic activity in the blood in the human autoimmune inflammatory disease asthma, those whose contribution to the asthmatic phenotype is not yet understood. Pathophysiologic activation of metabolic was evidenced by transcriptional induction of enzymes *OLAH* (oleoyl-ACP hydrolase), a gene functioning in fatty acid metabolism, *ASS1* (argininosuccinate synthase 1), *ARG1*, *GLUL*, and *TYR* (tyrosinase). Loss of T-bet expression in childhood asthma thus occurs in an altered metabolic environment. The combination of metabolites produced by activation of the enzymes described here is likely a requisite component for aggressive and sustained disease activity in humans with asthma.

GSE256534

References

1. Jia, X., Crawford, J.C., Gebregzabher, D., Monson, E.A., Mettelman, R.C., Wan, Y., Ren, Y., Chou, J., Novak, T., McQuilten, H.A. and Clarke, M., 2024. High expression of oleoyl-ACP hydrolase underpins life-threatening respiratory viral diseases. *Cell*, 187(17), pp.4586-4604.

2. Palanki, R., Yamagata, H. and Mitchell, M.J., 2024. OLAH connects fatty acid metabolism to the severity of respiratory viral disease. *Cell*, 187(17), pp.4549-4551.

3. Häberle, J., Görg, B., Rutsch, F., Schmidt, E., Toutain, A., Benoist, J.F., Gelot, A., Suc, A.L., Höhne, W., Schliess, F. and Häussinger, D., 2005. Congenital glutamine deficiency with glutamine synthetase mutations. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 353(18), pp.1926-1933.

4. Munder, M., Eichmann, K. and Modolell, M., 1998. Alternative metabolic states in murine macrophages reflected by the nitric oxide synthase/arginase balance: competitive regulation by CD4+ T cells correlates with Th1/Th2 phenotype. *The Journal of Immunology*, 160(11), pp.5347-5354.

5. Munder, M., Schneider, H., Luckner, C., Giese, T., Langhans, C.D., Fuentes, J.M., Kropf, P., Mueller, I., Kolb, A., Modolell, M. and Ho, A.D., 2006. Suppression of T-cell functions by human granulocyte arginase. *Blood*, 108(5), pp.1627-1634.

6. Finotto, S., Neurath, M. F., Glickman, J. N., Qin, S., Lehr, H. A., Green, F. H., ... & Glimcher, L. H. (2002). Development of spontaneous airway changes consistent with human asthma in mice lacking T-bet. *Science*, 295(5553), 336-338.

7. Band, V. I., Gribonika, I., Stacy, A., Bouladoux, N., Mistry, S., Burns, A., Perez-Chaparro, P. J., Chau, J., Enamorado, M., Nagai, M., Bhushan, V., Golec, D. P., Schwartzberg, P. L., Hourigan, S. K., Nita-Lazar, A., & Belkaid, Y. (2025). Sulfide is a keystone metabolite for gut homeostasis and immunity. *bioRxiv* : the preprint server for biology, 2025.03.06.641928. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.03.06.641928>